

THE EFFECT OF TILLAGE IN VARIOUS WAYS ON THE THICKNESS OF A POROUS SEEDLING

Karabaev Ikramjan Turaevich

Research Institute of Cotton Breeding, Seed Production and Cultivation
Agrotechnology. Tashkent, Uzbekistan E-mail: ikromjon@gmail.com

Atabaeva Mamura Sadridin qizi

DSc Doctoral student of Andijan Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnology.
Andijan, Uzbekistan E-mail: mamura@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7619277>

Introduction. Today, thanks to the widespread introduction of advanced soil-protecting resource-saving technologies in agriculture into world agricultural practice, a reduction in the cost of production is achieved by improving the agronomic properties of land, growing high and high-quality crops and saving fuel and lubricants. Soil protection technologies are being implemented worldwide on a total area of more than 10 million hectares.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 17, 2019 No. 5742 "On the effective use of land and water resources in agriculture", Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2020 No. 4575 "On measures to implement in 2020 the tasks set in the strategy for the development of agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The degree of study of the problem: It is known that the wheels of high-performance technical means, as a result of the negative impact on the physical properties of the soil, microbiological processes occurring in it, lead to seed germination and plant growth, as well as a sharp decrease in yield. To Uzbekistan P .Nazarov, F.Khasanov, A.Sindirov, A.Khamrakulov [1; B. 2-3], F.Khasanova [2; B. 5], A.Yakubdzhonov [3; B. 391, 137; B. 358], H.Tursunav [4; B. 23], A.Yangiboev [5; B. 11-12] it is noted that when applying the technology of sowing seeds in seedlings, the ground is leveled in autumn, which is due to a reduction in agrotechnical measures in early spring, saving fuel and lubricants, a higher temperature than on flat ground, up to 1-30c, germination 2-4 days ago, reduced water consumption during irrigation.

Research methodology. Light gray, mechanical composition of the OK Water Experimental farm Kurgontepa district of Andijan region - medium loamy, unsalted, groundwater is located at a depth of 4-5 meters, the amount of humus (humus) in the Haidovsky (0-30 cm) soil layer is 0.8-0.9%, the nitrogen content of the total forms of nutrients is 0.05-0.09%, is. According to the mechanical composition, the medium and light clod varies from the composition to the

composition of a heavy clod, the proportion of large dust particles is 44-51%, and small dust particles is 30-40%.

Studies have shown that in 2018-2020, with a 2:1 crop rotation system (grain:cereals) varieties "Antonina" from autumn wheat, "salomat" from peanuts were grown as a repeat crop after autumn wheat, "Dormon" from lentils, "Rovot" from beans, "Jahangir" from sunflower., next year, the care of the wheat variety "Andijan 36" as the main crop was carried out on based on the following experimental system (Table 1)

Table 1

EXPERIENCE SYSTEM

№	Processing methods and depths	The main type of culture	Types of repeated crops	The main type of culture	The main type of culture
		2018/2019 y	2019 y.	2020 y.	2021 y.
1	Plowing the earth to a constant depth of 35-40 cm +boronization+molting+getting pus + planting (control)	Winter wheat	Lentil	Cotton	Cotton
2			peanut		
3			Sunflower		
4			Beans		
5	Planting a bush to a height of 30-35 cm in one step, cultivating the ground to a constant depth of 35-40 cm.	Winter wheat	Lentil	Cotton	Cotton
6			peanut		
7			Sunflower		
8			Beans		
9	Cultivation in a minimal way for winter wheat and repeated sowing (to a depth of 10-12 cm) + plowing to a depth of 35-40 cm when caring for a goose + getting a bush + planting.	Winter wheat	Lentil	Cotton	Cotton
10			peanut		
11			Sunflower		
12			Beans		
13	Autumn crops with a desk and doubles are limited to processing by the food method (drinking 10-12 cm) + processing of a gift of 35-40 cm KA'rihihi, take one pashto 30-35 cm high + planting	Winter wheat	Lentil	Cotton	Cotton
14			peanut		
15			Sunflower		
16			Beans		

17	Cultivation of the earth to a constant depth of 35-40 cm, unilateral bringing of the bush to a height of 30-35 cm, nitrogen application under the bush in the form of liquid ammonia in the amount of 100 kg / ha + planting	Winter wheat	Lentil	Cotton	Cotton
18			peanut		
19			Sunflower		
20			Beans		
21	For winter wheat and repeated crops, the minimum processing method (to a depth of 10-12 cm) + processing to a depth of 35-40 cm. When caring for a goose in one step, take a feather at a height of 30-35 cm and put nitrogen under the bush in the form of liquid ammonia in the amount of 100 kg / ha + planting	Winter wheat	Lentil	Cotton	Cotton
22			peanut		
23			Sunflower		
24			Beans		

In the course of the 2018/2019 research, a field of winter wheat was carried out to a depth of 35-40 cm, Haid and other measures were carried out, and then seeds were sown (2018) against the background of 1 (1-4 var.). It was noted that the thickness of seedlings is 326.9 thousand pcs/ha, and the soil is 323.0 on 3-4-6 backgrounds sown in special workshops in one way, when processing 323.6 thousand pcs/ha using a combined unit, and 336.8-335.2 thousand pcs/ha on 2-5 backgrounds obtained in one way.

After harvesting autumn wheat, repeated crops were processed in the ground in various ways and to a depth before planting to maintain, seeds of lentils, peanuts, sunflower and beans were sown and the thickness of seedlings was analyzed.

In fund 1, where the land is processed in the traditional way, the thickness of seedlings is 220.8 thousand pieces/ha of lentils, 99.6 thousand pieces/ha of peanuts, 50.1 thousand pieces/ha of sunflower and 214.7 thousand pieces/hectares of legumes, with minimal cultivation of the land at a time, are planted in special seeders 3-4-6. 206,7; 202,1; 205,7 in lentil crops, 89,6 in peanut crops, 89,1; 88,9 in sunflower crops, 49,6; 49,1 48,7 in bean crops, 211,7; 207,0; Up to 209,8 thousand. pcs/ha. On 2-5 backgrounds obtained at a time

during processing with a combined unit, the thickness of seedlings was observed up to 254.9-249.9 in lentils, 99.8-102.9 in peanuts, 54.3-55.1 in sunflower and 227.2-214.9 thousand units/ha in legumes.

Winter wheat, repeated sowing of peanuts, then next year again the continuous area for caring for the goose is 35-40 cm deep in 2 variants of Haydov, the thickness of goose seedlings is 85.8 thousand pcs./ ha, and other repeated crops (lentils, sunflower, beans), which are cared for during this processing method were determined in the course of observations at the end.

For the cultivation of winter wheat and repeated sowing, a set of measures was carried out for plowing to a depth of 35-40 cm to care for a goose planted in one way, tillage to a depth of 10-12 cm (minimum method), as a repeat crop on the 3rd background, when planting seeds, it was noticed that the thickness of seedlings by 0.2-4.8 thousand pcs/ha is higher compared to the background.

Cultivation of the earth to a depth of 35-40 cm with constant (when caring for all crops) one-sided planting in pink, taking pink to a height of 30-35 CM.in in the 6th variant, where peanuts were grown as a repeat crop, the thickness of goose seedlings was 86.8 thousand pieces/ha, compared with other repeat crops (lentils, high to/ha.

Like autumn wheat and a crop for transplanting, the plum is treated in the soil for care in a minimal way (to a depth of 10-12 cm), treated with a combined unit in Goose care to a depth of 35-40 cm, in the 14th variant, where seeds are planted with a bush 30-35 cm high. It was noticed that it was 3.2-7.8 thousand pieces higher than the background.

When working in the soil using combined aggregates, processing to a depth of 35-40 cm, unilateral reception of pushta to a height of 30-35 cm and nitrogen support in autumn under a bush without liquid ammonia in the amount of 100 kg / ha.- in the variant, the density of goose seedlings is 92.3 thousand pcs. / ha, which, compared with other repeated crops that were cared for on these backgrounds, were processed to a depth of 4.3-7.1 thousand pcs., with a constant depth of 35-40 cm, planted in a lump to a height of 30-35 cm.

Table 2

Introduction into the soil by various methods and to a depth, winter wheat, repeated sowing and thickness of goose seedlings, thousand pcs./ha (2018-2020)

№	Processing methods and depths	Winter wheat (2018.)	Repeated crops (2019 y.)	The goose (2020)
---	-------------------------------	----------------------	--------------------------	------------------

				y.)
1	Plowing the earth to a constant depth of 35-40 cm +boronization+molting+getting pus + planting (control)	326,9	220,8	83,9
2			99,6	85,8
3			50,1	81,2
4			214,7	83,5
5	Planting a bush to a height of 30-35 cm in one step, cultivating the ground to a constant depth of 35-40 cm.	336,8	204,9	84,9
6			99,8	86,8
7			54,3	82,1
8			227,2	84,4
9	Cultivation in a minimal way for winter wheat and repeated sowing (to a depth of 10-12 cm) + plowing to a depth of 35-40 cm when caring for a goose + getting a bush + planting.	323,0	206,7	84,1
10			89,6	86,0
11			49,6	81,4
12			211,7	83,7
13	Autumn crops with a desk and doubles are limited to processing by the food method (drinking 10-12 cm) + processing of a gift of 35-40 cm KA'ri hihi, take one pashto 30-35 cm high + planting	325,1	202,1	87,1
14			89,1	89,0
15			49,1	84,2
16			207,0	86,6
17	Cultivation of the earth to a constant depth of 35-40 cm, unilateral bringing of the bush to a height of 30-35 cm, nitrogen application under the bush in the form of liquid ammonia in the amount of 100 kg / ha + planting	335,2	209,9	88,0
18			102,9	92,3
19			55,1	85,2
20			214,9	87,6
21	For winter wheat and repeated crops, the minimum processing method (to a depth of 10-12 cm) + processing to a depth of 35-40 cm. When caring for a goose in one step, take a feather at a height of 30-35 cm and put nitrogen under the bush in the form of liquid ammonia in the amount of 100 kg / ha + planting	323,6	205,7	91,6
22			88,9	94,5
23			48,7	86,8
24			209,8	90,1

To grow peanuts as autumn wheat and spring crops, the soil is treated in a minimal way (10-12 cm), and then the area for caring for the goose is treated to a depth of 35-40 cm, bringing the bush to a height of 30-35 cm in one step and introducing nitrogen under the bush in the form of- in the variant, the density of goose seedlings was 94.5 thousand pcs / ha, compared with other repeated crops (lentils, sunflower, beans) grown on these backgrounds, up to 2.9-7.7 thousand pcs./ha, compared with the 1st background, where constant processing was carried out, up to 8.7-13.3 thousand. pcs/ha, compared with the 2nd in relation to the background, up to 8.4-13.1 thousand pcs/ha, winter wheat, minimum for growing repeated crops, it was noticed that the combination for pit care is up to 5.5-10.3 thousand units compared to the 4th background treated with filler, and a continuous combination of 2.2-9.3 thousand. Doan/ha is higher than the 5th background with liquid ammonia under the bush.

In conclusion, we note that mumkinki, Yorga Minal ishlov berib method, deer bodies and its ecological reporter minimal ishlov berishiak method resurstezhakora agrologiyasin ullaba, daily grown as a combination unit elamida ishlov berib, bir illa pushta olsh, pushta ostiga azottate ammoate 100 kg relative to a mountain fire in the mountainous region of kalinligakar etishtirilganda 6,2, the traditional method of islov berylganda 11,4, permanent Barch ekinstvuyushchy combinator unit assistant ishlow berylganda 9,6, steam kuzg and duplicated ekinnisht, at least a method, he also grew up in haydov 11,8, permanently combined unit bidan ishlov berib, pushta ostiga Siuk ammonium 3.2 grain size less, bu this description of ethylaetgan technology is based on the fact that berysh jaraenid bergenid kuznein-kuznein-dehkandin, as well as on the basis of ethylaetgan technology as in the case of this disease, currently there are a number of reasons why you should avoid using ammonium.

List of used literature:

- 1.Nazirov R., Gasanov F., Sindarov A., Khamrakulov I. Sozдание optimal toltshini vskhodov na polyax. // Magazine selskoy ekonomiki Uzbekistana. 2010. № 3. B. 2-3.
- 2.Khasanova F.Technology polucheniya M-push. // Magazine selskogo hozyaystva Uzbekistana. Tashkent-2009 № 12. B. 5.
- 3.Yakubjanov O.- "Method poseva semyan I podkormki khlopka" yavlyayutsya osnovnimi napravleniyami uglubleniya I razvitiya fermerskikh khozyaystv v agrarnoy SERE. (Sbornik statey Republican nauchno-prakticheskoy konferentii) Andijan. 2007. B. 358

4. Tursunav X. "Method posadki i Vliyanie toltshini prorostkov na sort gusya Andijan-37" Uzbeksky magazine selskogo hozyaystva. 2012. №8. B. 23
5. Yangiboev A. - "Vodaberegayutshee Arashenie povishaet urojaynost xlopka". Magazine agronauki No. 1. 2009. B. 11-12

